

NODES – Nord Ovest Digitale e Sostenibile

FLAGSHIP PROJECT GRIP

SPOKE 2 –GREEN TECHNOLOGIES AND SUSTAINABLE INDUSTRIES

DELIVERABLE D2.6.1 “New characterized material from biomasses”

REPORTING PERIOD	
Period covered:	from M8 to M 28
Periodic report date and version:	30-09-2025
Deliverable # Responsible	Arlorio
RM2 Responsible	Arlorio

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Glossary

	Definition
Hub Coordinator (HC)	The Hub Coordinator represents the single point of contact for the implementation of the innovation ecosystem towards the MUR. It carries out the management and coordination activities of the innovation ecosystem, receives the fundings, verifies, and transmits to the MUR the reporting of the activities carried out by the Spoke and their affiliates.
National Recovery and Resilience Plan (NRRP)	This document uses the Italian acronym for the NRRP, which is PNRR (Piano Nazionale della Ripresa e Resilienza)
Research Program Manager	The person who will be the responsible for the overall scientific contents of the NODES project. The NODES will appoint the Research Program Manager. It refers to “Responsabile del Programma di Ricerca” in the MUR’s Call of proposal for “Ecosistemi di Innovazione”
NODES’ Research and innovation program	NODES’ Research and Innovation program is articulated in specific programs for each Spoke, with the aim to promote and support applied research on topics consistent with the Intelligent Specialization Strategy, with the guidelines of the 2021-2027 partnership agreement scheme, with regional operational plans and regional and national research and innovation priorities. Although NODES’ Spokes are concentrated on different themes, they will organize their activities and actions within a common framework – NODES’ Booster Methodology
Spoke Coordinator	The University in charge of coordinating the Spoke’s ecosystem. It refers to “Spoke” in the MUR’s Call of proposal for “Ecosistemi di Innovazione”
Spoke Data Manager	The person who will be the responsible for the monitoring and management of data generated at the Spoke level. The Spoke Coordinator will appoint the Spoke Data Manager.
Spoke Partner	The entity associated to the Spoke Coordinator. It can be an Innovation Cluster, Competence Center, Research Center related to the Spoke’s ecosystem and contributes to achieve objectives and impact under the Spoke’ leadership and management. It refers to “soggetti affiliati” in the MUR’s Call of proposal for “Ecosistemi di Innovazione”.
Spoke Project manager	The person who will be the responsible for the management, coordination and progress of the project at the Spoke level. The Spoke Coordinator will appoint the Spoke Project Manager.
Spoke research and innovation program	NODES’ Research and Innovation program is articulated in specific programs for each Spokes. The spoke will leverage a consolidated collaboration with leading private and public companies and will focus the applied research activity on technological domains and applications that can favour the integration of SMEs into new value chains.
Spoke Scientific and Technical Manager	The person who will be the responsible for the overall scientific contents of the project at the Spoke level. The Spoke Coordinator will appoint the Spoke Scientific and Technical Manager.
Spoke Stakeholders Committee (SC)	Consultation structure formed by relevant stakeholders (Government, universities, companies, civil society, third sector, etc.)
Spoke Thematic	General target focus and domain of the Spoke research.
Spoke Topics	Specific areas/lines of development within the Spoke.
Spoke Work Package Leader	At the Spoke level, Work Packages (WPs) will be organized by WP leaders, who will be responsible for performance evaluation and reporting.
Flagship Project	Main research project at the Spoke level with the goal of prototyping, testing, demonstrating the research activities towards higher TRLs.

List of Deliverables

D. No	Name	Type	Disseminati on Level	Due Date	Delivery Date (actual)
[number]	[name]	[R — Document, report] [DEM — Demonstrator, pilot, prototype] [DEC — Websites, patent filings, videos, etc] [DATA — data sets, microdata, etc] [DMP — Data Management Plan] [ETHICS] [SECURITY] [OTHER]	[PU — Public] [SEN — Sensitive] [R] [C] [S]	[month number]	[dd/mm/yyyy]
D2.1	Data about chemical and nutritional profiling of raw wastes and by products	R	PU	M14	18/04/2024
D2.2.1	On line lab-scale technical multi-device for waste processing*	Other (material)	PU	M18	25/10/2024
D2.2.2	Delivery of protocols (lab-scale) ready to scale-up the production of new high-value material (in collaboration with Companies)	R	PU	M22	16/02/2025
D2.3.1	New data about valorized matrices characterization and high value products	R	PU	M28	30/09/2025
D2.3.2	New characterized ingredients/materials for food, nutraceuticals, pharma and cosmetic applications	Other (material)	PU	M30	30/09/2025
D2.4.1	New data about sustainable production of new materials from biomasses	R	PU	M24	
D2.4.2	New characterized materials from biomasses	Other (material)	PU	M30	30/09/2025
D2.5.2	Porous sorbents from biomasses valorization	Other (material)	PU	M30	29/09/2025
D2.6.1	New material produced at pilot scale ready to the formulation or co-formulation (in collaboration with Companies)	Other (material)	PU	M32	30/09/2025
D2.6.2	New well characterized process and formulated pilot-products (in collaboration with Companies)	R/Other (Material)	PU	M32	

D2.7	Report on the adsorption and/or catalytic performances of porous solids derived from biomasses valorization and non-recyclable plastic wastes	R	PU	M32	29/09/2025
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A) INTRODUCTION

The main outcome reported in this Deliverable is related to the confirmation of the availability of the material (new ingredients rich in bioactive compounds) produced as pilot level, ready to be used in collaboration with Companies for the formulation of some selected “model products” (food supplements; cosmetic products, described in D 6.2.2).

B) ROLE OF PARTNERS

The Partner more involved in this activity was DSF-UPO, working in collaboration with Procemsa Company (Turin), ProgeFarm Company (Novara) and APTsol Company (Novara). The collaboration with the companies was strategic especially in the phase of the product formulation.

C) EXPLANATION OF THE WORK CARRIED OUT AND OVERVIEW OF THE PROGRESS

Following we synthetically report the list of the material selected for the pilot scale- up and ready for the formulation (as the result of the production and characterization as described in D2.3.1, D2.3.2 and D.2.4.2, and after a pilot scale-up useful to achieve a pilot production of final model product).

- *Prebiotic fiber/antioxidant polyphenols from cocoa bean husks*
- *Fiber from apple pomace*
- *Phloretin/phlorizin/polyphenol rich ingredients from apple pomace*
- *Polyphenols rich extract from blueberry pomace.*

All the material are available at DSF-UPO.